

HKR120, a promising new rice

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HKR120 is a promising, medium-duration (140-145 d) semidwarf

developed from Ptb 33/4*IR3403-267-1 at IRRI. Tested in the 1981 International Rice Observational Nursery, it showed good phenotypic acceptability. Under evaluation at HAURRS in 1982-84, it yielded more and had better tillering capacity than the checks PR106 and Jaya. It has yield

stability (see table) because it is resistant to bacterial blight (BB) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), which are major pests in Haryana. Its grains are long, slender, translucent, and have no white belly. Quality is as good as that of PR106. ✍

Performance of HKR120 in Haryana, India.

Variety	Av yield (t/ha) 1982-84	Duration (d)	Panicles/m ²	Milling (%)	Length: Width	Kernel elongation (mm)	Cooking quality	BB ^a (0-9 scale)	WBPH ^b (0-5 scale)	Rating ^c
HKR120	6.5	146	296	67	3.43	1.98	Good	3	0.73	R
PR106	6.1	148	313	67	3.25	1.98	Good	7	4.0	S
Jaya	6.0	147	298	71	2.86	1.76	Fair	7	4.5	S
CD at 5%	0.5	0.7	0.3							
CV%	5.4	7.5	3.9							

^a Based on the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^b Based on Kalode et al 1975. ^c R = resistant, S = susceptible.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Disease-resistant IRRI varieties in Tamil Nadu

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Between 1982 and 1984, blast (B1) and tungro virus (RTV) caused serious yield losses in Tamil Nadu. Commonly grown TKM9 and IR50 were susceptible to B1 and ADT31, ADT36, TKM9, and IR20, to RTV. We evaluated 37 IRRI rices for disease resistance at TNRRI in 1984-85 kuruvai (Jun planted) and thaladi (Sep planted).

For RTV screening in the glasshouse, 1 viruliferous green leafhopper that had fed for 4 d on RTV-infected plants was placed on each 10-d-old seedling for 2 d. For B1 screening in the greenhouse, 15-d-old seedlings were spray-inoculated with a conidial suspension (20,000 cells/ml) of the B1 fungus and kept in polythene tents in high humidity for 24 h before and after spraying. The varieties were also field-screened under natural conditions with 100 kg applied N/ha. Disease incidence was scored by

Disease resistance of IRRI varieties in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Disease infection								
	RTV(%)		Leaf Bl		Neck				
	Glasshouse	Field	Greenhouse (0-9)	Field (%)	B1 (%)	ShR (%)	BS (0-9)	BLB (0-9)	G1D (%)
IR9179-209-2-2-2-3	8	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0
IR13423-10-2-3	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	1	Stray
IR13429-299-2-1-3-1 (IR60)	4	0	0	0	0	3	3	1	0
IR1 7494-32-1-1-3-2	16	8	0	0	1	3	1	5	
IR18349-53-1-3-1-3	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	5	
IR24632-34-2	14	0	0	0	5	3	3	10	
IR31802-48-2-2-2	8	0	0	0	3	3	1	10	
IR32307-10-2-1-1	10	0	0	0	1	3	3	0	
IR32385-37-3-3-3	24	0	0	0	3	3	1	0	
IR32429-47-3-2	19	0	0	0	3	3	1	0	
IR32429-68-3-3-3	7	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	
IR13423-17-1-2-1	0	0	5	4	0	1	1	5	
IR13927-40-2-3-3-3-3	0	0	3	1	0	3	3	1	0
IR28143-66-3-3-2	0	0	5	37	0	1	3	1	5
IR31851-63-1-2-3-2	0	0	7	60	0	0	3	1	2
IR31868-64-2-3-3-3	0	0	5	3	0	3	3	0	9
IR29725-3-1-3-2	0	0	3	5	1	3	3	3	0
IR54	18	5.9	0	0	0	3	3	1	5
IR58	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	Stray	0
IR50	0	0	7	50	40	5	5	3	5
Co33	62	57.6	7	62	58	7	5	9	10
TKM9	65	60.0	7	53	45	5	5	3	5
ADT36	70	58.5	3	6	0	5	3	5	5
IR20	48	45.0	3	4	0	3	3	3	2

the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale (see table).

Only RTV was present in kuruvai. In thaladi, RTV, B1, sheath rot (ShR),

brown spot (BS), bacterial leaf blight (BLB), and grain discoloration (G1D) were common. Evaluation of these selections will continue in 1985. ✍